

Is Machine Learning Beneficial to Humans: Is the Risk Worth the Gains?

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Abstract

Is machine learning beneficial to humans? The concept of letting machines learning sounds amazing but we often forget the negative impacts of such. Could we really trust the capabilities of machine learning in a world where everyday a new discovery is being found? In this report I hope to see how people would react about machine learning at first and then how they react after presenting negative and positive consequences. I will be conducting a survey on a sample of people with the age ranging from 10-75. Together these findings will tell if machine learning is beneficial to humans and the risks that are with it is truly worth it.

Keywords: Machine Learning, Fear, Consequences

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To fully understand this study we have to understand what is machine learning. Machine learning is the study of computer algorithms and systems that substantially improve automatically through experience. It goes hand in hand with the study and it is seen as one of the main elements of artificial intelligence. In this study we will be using self driving/car related accidents to model the data.

Method**Participants**

I have surveyed one hundred people and asked them the following questions:

Impressions on machine learning?

Would you trust cars that use machine learning in your day to day life?

After these questions I present to them two accidents that machine learning was in fault then I asked them:

Would you like to change your answers from the questions I have asked previously?

Assessments and Measures

In November of 2019 a self-driving Uber car has hit a pedestrian. The results of this was that the car lacked the inability to differentiate it between an object and a person. I presented this first case into the study. In March of 2018 a Tesla got in a car crash and the driver was killed. The autopilot has failed in driving the car and this was the second case I introduced into the study. From presenting these cases I expected a change in answers and mainly mood in the topic of safety.

Should we be Necessarily Scared?

Based on the data available to us self driving accidents are quite rare and not as common as you think however as the industry is developing and changing to help fight climate change machine learning will be very common sooner than later.

Is Machine Learning inevitably the future?

Machine learning is the future in every field you can possibly think of. Like everything there is always a negative but the negative should be ignored to an extent. In most cases the future will consist of accidents that are the fault of the human and not the machine. The machine can be wrong but ultimately the human will be the downfall of the machine.

Do we use machine learning in our everyday life?

As stated above machine learning is in every field you can possibly think of. It is primarily being used right now in cyber security and privacy. The best example is Apple's Iphone X. The Iphone X uses machine learning to convey their face ID technology. Anything you can think of on the internet probably has an AI and/or an element of machine learning.

Results

This study concludes that most people are open to machine learning and not necessarily afraid of it when they do not hear examples of accidents. In a survey of 100 people with age range from 10-75 the results are posted below.

Outcome 1

When asked this question the overwhelming answer was yes. The participants knew and understood the benefits of machine learning and/or AI. However when presented with the negatives there was an instant change of mood and heart.

Would you trust cars that use machine learning in your day to day life?

Survey of 100 people

Outcome 2

After presenting the cases as mentioned above there was an instant feeling of regret that was present in most participants. Most people often agree that their answer changes when

evaluating the benefits and negatives in a topic.

Would you like to change your answers from the questions I have asked previously?

Discussion

These data are based upon people from the ages of 10-75 and this experiment was done in New York City. It is clear that the rise of machine learning is something to be cherished as well as something to be aware of. Machine learning ultimately should be studied upon carefully since a single computational error can be the difference of a person being alive or dead.

References

There were no references in this study.